

On the role of SecRAM catalogues in ATM Cyber Risk Assessment and improvement opportunities

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Abstract—Current Air Traffic Management (ATM) systems are undergoing significant evolution due to increased traffic volumes, the introduction of diverse airborne systems such as Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), technological advancements, and the potential to optimize operations through data-driven approaches. These advancements offer benefits in terms of efficiency, safety, and sustainability, but they also expose the systems to heightened cybersecurity risks. This paper analyzes the Security Risk Assessment Methodology (SecRAM) proposed by SESAR, focusing specifically on its use of complementary catalogs of threats and vulnerabilities. By validating the SecRAM approach in a contemporary ATM scenario, this paper identifies gaps in the framework that could be addressed to better meet the security needs of a modern and complex ATM ecosystem. Finally, this work proposes a set of enhancements to the SecRAM catalogs that will enable security professionals to design and develop secure and resilient modern ATM environments.

Keywords—ATM, FCI, risk-assessment, security, SecRAM.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, ATM ecosystem has been developing new capabilities to enhance operational efficiency, safety, and sustainability. These modern features, established within the ATM context, aim to exploit available information to optimize resource consumption and better coordinate with all stakeholders involved in airspace management. These factors are shaping a future ATM environment that is constantly evolving and must be dynamically managed to support complex scenarios involving coordination among multiple stakeholders. In this context of evolving requirements, a proposal for the future architecture of European airspace was developed by the SESAR Joint Undertaking [1]. This proposal seeks to address the increasing challenge of airspace capacity by decoupling ATM services from physical infrastructures, exploiting modern virtualization capabilities, and increasing the level of collaboration and automation. This approach aims to achieve de-fragmentation of EU skies and optimization of airspace usage according to operational needs that cross national boundaries and thus require coordination across different flight information regions.

This capability enhancement is strongly coupled with the concept of the Future Communication Infrastructure [2], as defined by SESAR. This refers to a resilient data-link infrastructure designed to support modern services necessary for the advancement of ATM capabilities. The network infrastructure will be equipped to handle high levels of air traffic—both manned and unmanned—with increasing communication demands. Future air-to-ground communication will

require greater capacity and enhanced performance compared to the current Air Traffic Network (ATN). A key technological advancement in this context is the adoption of the Internet Protocol as the basis for all ATN communications to enhance current network capabilities. Consequently, the future infrastructure will enable services based on high-density data sharing capabilities, involving a broader set of stakeholders distributed across a geographically expansive area. This architecture will be crucial for the safety-critical coordination of air traffic in both the civil and military sectors. One innovative approach being introduced is the Trajectory-Based Optimization (TBO) paradigm [3], which utilizes 4D trajectory data to optimize routes and flight paths.

The adoption of modern ATM operations heralds a new era of integrated air traffic management where stakeholders collaborate by sharing information to enhance efficiency. These paradigms depend heavily on advanced data exchange capabilities, automation, and complex algorithms to manage increasingly intricate air traffic. However, this heightened interconnectivity within service architectures introduces a set of security concerns and challenges that could potentially compromise the integrity and reliability of the ATM system.

Cyber-attacks on aviation systems have a well-documented history, illustrating the vulnerability of these critical infrastructures. For example, in 1997, an attack on Worcester Airport's control system disabled the phone systems for six hours, halting communications for the control tower, airport security, and fire control [4]. A more recent instance occurred in 2015 when a denial of service attack on LOT Polish Airlines' systems resulted in the cancellation of 10 flights, stranding a total of 1,400 passengers [5]. Another prevalent form of attack involves the manipulation of GNSS data, which has become a mainstream and well-documented issue in certain regions of the world [6], leading to incorrect system localization.

These examples underscore the critical importance of cybersecurity in any avionic system to ensure resiliency and robustness. One of the initial steps to provide strong cybersecurity guarantees is to implement an enhanced and continuous security risk assessment process. This process will guide the design, operation, and maintenance of the overall system, ensuring that appropriate security measures are effectively implemented. In a context where the architecture is predominantly distributed, the traditional approach—where each component and each stakeholder conducts their own security risk

assessment—falls short of securing the overall architecture. It is essential to ensure system-wide integration through seamless coordination across different stakeholders in the avionics sector. Consequently, a comprehensive risk assessment framework that enables domain experts and security professionals to identify, evaluate, and mitigate potential security threats is critical to guaranteeing resilience and robustness.

SESAR has introduced a risk assessment methodology termed SecRAM [7], which provides a structured approach that security professionals and avionic experts can utilize for conducting security risk assessments. This methodology includes catalogs that detail descriptions and taxonomies of assets, threats, vulnerabilities, and mitigation strategies. Adopting these catalogs is vital for fostering collaboration among different stakeholders, serving as a common knowledge base and offering a standardized framework for various organizations and experts. However, the current state of the SecRAM catalogs reveals significant gaps with respect to state-of-the-art ATM, focusing more on historical components and lacking attention to modern IT-based systems that are now integral to contemporary systems. In this context, the authors perform a gap analysis and identify opportunities for improvement that will enable stakeholders to address a broader spectrum of threats and vulnerabilities, both within individual systems and collaboratively across the future ATM infrastructure.

This paper is organized as follows: Section II discusses the background and related work used in this study as a baseline. Section III details the step-by-step methodology used to evaluate the current risk assessment methodology, SecRAM, and the use case to which it was applied. Section IV highlights the identified gaps in SecRAM and proposes a set of improvements to enhance the methodology, making it more suitable for application in modern ATM contexts. Finally, Section V summarizes the research outcomes and outlines potential future directions for expanding this research.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

Threat and vulnerability analysis is an essential part of cybersecurity management. It is aimed at identifying and addressing potential security vulnerabilities that attackers could exploit. By systematically evaluating these vulnerabilities, organizations can strategically prioritize security measures based on the severity and likelihood of threats [8]. This helps improve their overall security posture and resilience against cyberattacks. This proactive approach not only mitigates risks but also ensures the efficient allocation of resources to protect critical areas effectively and economically [9]. Furthermore, such analyses are crucial for compliance with regulatory requirements and for maintaining stakeholder trust. They are indispensable for proactive risk management and ensuring operational sustainability amidst various challenges.

Building on this foundation, recent research has increasingly focused on enhancing the cybersecurity of safety-critical systems. In 2014, an approach called CORAS was introduced, utilizing a model-based methodology for compositional risk modeling in large systems [10]. This method addresses the

intricacies of security risk assessment in expansive system architectures. Although these studies provide valuable frameworks for assessing risks in complex systems, they fall short in exploring the collaborative engagement of different stakeholders and the use of catalogues as a means of coordination.

Mantzana et al. propose a centralized framework for managing cyber-physical risks in critical infrastructures, such as airports, advocating for the establishment of a centralized entity to streamline communication and cooperation among various operators and stakeholders [11]. While this research contributes significantly to general security management, it does not delve deeply into specific strategies for cyber-security risk assessment. The existing cybersecurity risk assessment methodologies, such as CORAS, provide valuable frameworks to enhance security in various sectors. However, these methodologies are not directly applicable to the aviation industry due to its unique operational environment and stringent safety requirements. The aviation sector, with its safety-critical requirements, complex regulatory landscape, and high cost of disruptions, necessitates specialized security assessment methodologies. Additionally, the aviation industry faces specific challenges, such as ensuring secure interoperability across global networks and dealing with legacy systems that were not originally designed with cybersecurity in mind [12].

Security Risk Assessment methodologies generally encompass several critical steps, with the identification of potential threats and the selection of appropriate security controls being particularly complex and time-consuming. Previous studies have underscored this complexity, highlighting the significant resources required for these processes [13], [14]. To assist in these tasks, the use of checklists and catalogues has been proposed and proven effective, especially in the aviation and ATM sectors. Research by Gramatica et al. [15] demonstrated that when combined with prior security knowledge, catalogues enable practitioners to identify the most appropriate cybersecurity threats and controls with confidence. Additionally, Bergström et al. [16], [17] noted that catalogues play a pivotal role in reducing language barriers, thereby establishing a shared and common vocabulary among diverse stakeholders.

SecRAM methodology was introduced by SESAR in 2020 as a specialized approach for risk assessment, building upon the ISO/IEC 27005 framework [7]. This methodology provides security professionals with the necessary tools to identify threats, vulnerabilities, and potential mitigation strategies within the aviation ecosystem. To evaluate the adoption and utility of these catalogues, Bergström et al. conducted interviews with ATM professionals, gaining insights into the advantages of using catalogues within risk assessment methodologies [18]. The findings highlight how catalogues ensure consistency and provide a common reference point for professionals involved in securing the same system. While SecRAM catalogues enhance collaborative efforts among stakeholders in complex system security risk assessments, their applicability may be somewhat limited and not extend to all scenarios.

Bernsmed et al. delve into the development of the SecRAM methodology and pose an important question regarding what

is hindering its complete adoption in the ATM context [19]. They propose an inductive methodology to evaluate how practitioners perceive the application of SecRAM and discuss the results of their findings. Interestingly, the two major outcomes of the interviews focused on tooling support and catalogues. Concerning the specifics of the catalogues, they are perceived as useful for (1) kick-starting the risk assessment process, (2) ensuring consistency, (3) favoring the reuse of previous work related to subsystems or components, and (4) facilitating links between recurring concepts.

The study conducted in this paper aims to address and answer the following research questions:

- 1) How does incompleteness in SecRAM pose critical risks to aviation safety?
- 2) How can mapping threat scenarios to SecRAM reveal gaps in its threat and vulnerability coverage, and how does this improve the aviation sector's security and resilience against cyber attacks?
- 3) How can integrating ontologies enhance SecRAM's effectiveness and usability, and how can the catalogs be kept up to date with minimal effort?
- 4) What measures can be taken to increase stakeholder trust in SecRAM and promote its widespread adoption?

III. METHODOLOGY AND USE CASE

This research outlines a methodology designed to enhance the viability of SecRAM threats and vulnerabilities catalogues for the security analysis of modern and future ATM systems. By integrating domain expertise, use-case specific data, and insights from public reports, this approach aims to identify and address existing gaps in these catalogues. The improved comprehensiveness and relevance of the SecRAM will enable users to bolster their security analysis capabilities and awareness, ultimately benefiting the overall cyber-security posture of the ATM SecRAM ecosystem.

The seven-step methodology used is explained as follows:

- 1) *Use-case Driven Security Analysis Scope Definition*: The gap analysis begins with a detailed definition of the use case architecture and the boundaries of the security analysis. This step involves identifying all pertinent systems, processes, applications, components, and data flows under consideration. Additionally, Product Life-Cycle Phases (LCP) are determined as part of the security analysis scope definition. The goal is to ensure that the SecRAM catalogues account for all potential threats and attacks that may occur during various phases, such as production, delivery, operation, and decommissioning.
- 2) *Assets Identification*: The scope of the Security Analysis also guides the identification of Supporting Assets (SA) that are subject to threat and vulnerability assessments.
- 3) *Literature Review*: Following the definition of the scope, a comprehensive literature review was conducted to uncover documented threat scenarios and associated vulnerabilities. This review included academic research and industry reports to gather insights into both current and emerging cybersecurity threats within the aviation

sector. The focus on Threat Scenarios is a strategic decision aimed at making the gap assessment as tangible as possible. Given the practical application of SecRAM within the ATM community, there is an expectation that the Cyber Risk Assessment methodology will help identify specific risk scenarios impacting the systems and technologies currently in use. Therefore, we have chosen to base our gap analysis on the most up-to-date knowledge and field expertise.

- 4) *Threat Scenarios Identification*: This step involves identifying threat scenarios based on both literature and the expertise of the security professionals involved. The identified threat scenarios are cataloged in a table designed to facilitate: (1) linking each scenario to the corresponding Supporting Asset, (2) assigning the scenario to the appropriate life-cycle phase, and (3) noting the source reference for each identification.
- 5) *Human Factor Analysis*: This analysis leverages a state-of-the-art review, the expertise of cyber-security analysts specializing in human factors, and data gathered from interviews and questionnaires distributed to key use case stakeholders. The outcome is a comprehensive set of human-related and organizational Threat Scenarios. These insights significantly enrich the outcomes of traditional vulnerability and threat analyses.
- 6) *Mapping to SecRAM catalogues*: The identified threat scenarios from the analysis are mapped to the SecRAM Threat and Vulnerability catalogues. This mapping may yield different results depending on the specific threats and vulnerabilities. In some instances, SecRAM may be found adequate, providing thorough threat coverage and descriptions that are accurate and relevant to the ATM domain. However, there are instances where certain threat scenarios are not adequately covered, necessitating the addition of new entries to the catalogues. Similarly, in some cases, the descriptions may require refinement or tailoring to better suit the ATM domain. Another aspect of evaluation involves assessing the categorization of threats — determining how easily threats can be identified and whether the categories could be enhanced for better usability. All findings from this process are documented in the form of comments. A similar approach is applied to vulnerability entries, with any gaps also being carefully noted in the comments.
- 7) *SecRAM Gaps Analysis*: Based on the feedback gathered during the mapping activity, a series of improvements for the SecRAM Threat and Vulnerability catalogues are proposed. These enhancements aim to improve usability, increase accuracy, and ensure the catalogues' relevance to the ATM sector. Additionally, the suggested improvements are intended to raise awareness and understanding of threats and vulnerabilities within the ATM domain.

A. Use Case

The methodology was applied to a use case involving a Trajectory-Based Operations (TBO) ATM scenario, with a

focus on the end-to-end data flow between aircraft and ground systems. TBO allows the ATM system to adjust both the planned and actual flight trajectories, either before or during a flight, using accurate, real-time information shared by all stakeholders. This collaborative approach enhances efficiency for both airspace users and the network. Figure 1 provides a high-level overview of the key components involved in the use case, illustrating how they interact to realize the TBO concept, and defines the specific scope for the security analysis conducted in this study.

In this scenario, TBO-related information is exchanged between the pilot and the controller. The use case includes human actors responsible for system operations, following procedures defined by TBO functionality. The end systems utilize advanced services (e.g., 4DTRAD [20]) to communicate TBO-related information to human counterparts. The 4DTRAD system leverages Controller Pilot Data Link Communications (CPDLC) and Automatic Dependent Surveillance–Contract (ADS-C) datalinks to transmit messages into the IPS-based network. The air-to-ground link is established using available radio technologies, such as the L-band Digital Aeronautical Communication System (LDACS). Upon receiving the message on the ground, the packets are routed through the IPS network to the intended recipient’s end system, where protocol decapsulation extracts the relevant TBO data.

Figure 1 illustrates that the system components categorized as “Technical Factors” can be divided into distinct layers: the radio link layer, the network layer, and the ATS and Datalink Application layer. Additionally, “Human and Procedural Factors” are highlighted, identifying the role of human actors (such as pilots, controllers, and maintainers) and the procedures involved in TBO operations and maintenance. To emphasize the security scope within the use case, the diagram highlights in orange the architectural building blocks—whether human, procedural, or technical—that will be subjected to the previously described methodological steps.

IV. FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

Among the nine partners, five conducted a thorough threat analysis of the identified 12 security domains, mapping them to 46 unique supporting assets relevant to the use case scenarios. Each partner focused on specific domains to assess threat scenarios, reviewing 76 documents, including research papers and reports, to understand the security landscape of modern ATM systems. This review identified 149 threat scenarios, each described with details such as the targeted system lifecycle phase and the impacted security assets and properties—confidentiality, integrity, availability, and non-repudiation. The objective of this effort was not to list all possible threats but to evaluate the SecRAM methodology’s effectiveness, identify gaps, and suggest improvements for enhanced threat-vulnerability assessment of ATM systems.

A. Identified Gaps in SecRAM 2.0

SEC-AIRSPACE team, comprised of aerospace security professionals, conducted a threat analysis based on a spe-

cific use case. The resulting data was utilized to perform a comprehensive gap analysis of the SecRAM catalogue. Each identified threat from the scenarios was aligned with the most closely related threat in the SecRAM catalogue, a process that required considerable adaptation and interpretive flexibility. Additionally, the analysis included a vulnerability analysis, identifying vulnerabilities susceptible to these threats and mapping them to corresponding entries in the catalogue.

Of the 64 threats listed in the SecRAM catalogue, only 33 were relevant to the scenarios analyzed by SEC-AIRSPACE. This discrepancy primarily stems from many threats in SecRAM focusing on physical security, which did not align with the cyber-focused scenarios analyzed. The findings revealed that the existing threats in SecRAM are predominantly tailored to IT systems and do not adequately address the complexity of cyber-physical systems prevalent in the aerospace sector. The insights and recommendations in Table I aim to refine the SecRAM threat and vulnerability catalogue.

To ensure the relevance and accuracy of this ATM-specific resource, it is recommended that the SecRAM catalogue align with publicly maintained catalogues, which are regularly updated by a broad community of security experts. This strategy would minimize maintenance efforts and ensure that the catalogue stays aligned with current security practices, thereby enhancing its applicability and effectiveness in aviation.

B. Threat Landscaping through Categorization: A Proposal

To enhance security assessments within the aviation sector, we propose a threat categorization framework. Drawing inspiration from established models like CAPEC, ATT&CK, and CWE, we have categorized all SecRAM threats into distinct groups as outlined in Appendix A1. These groups include the type of supporting assets, cyber and non-cyber vectors, asset locations—whether ground or airspace, the lifecycle stages of assets (e.g. production, deployment, ...), and the level of sophistication or complexity of the threats. This nuanced analysis is designed to be of value to aviation equipment manufacturers, ATM staff, aviation service providers, network administrators and cybersecurity managers, airport authorities, etc. It equips these stakeholders to develop tailored policies, awareness programs, and robust security measures safeguarding the aviation ecosystem.

1) *Categorization based on types of Supporting Assets (SA):* This category organizes threats by key components such as software, hardware, physical infrastructure, communication networks, human factors, and media. It enables a detailed evaluation of how each component can be exploited and the potential impact on security. This categorization offers substantial benefits to various stakeholders. It provides a detailed view of potential vulnerabilities and facilitates the development of targeted security protocols that protect critical infrastructure. For example, manufacturers can enhance security features during design and production to protect against hardware tampering, while communication network providers can strengthen defences against cyber intrusions. Additionally, the focus on human factors underscores the importance of

Figure 1. High-Level Security Scope of Trajectory Based Operations

TABLE I. SUMMARY OF PROPOSED CHANGES TO THE SecRAM 2.0 CATALOGUE

Category	Description
Titles	Revisions or enhancements proposed for the titles of 3 threats.
Descriptions	Extensions and improvements suggested for the descriptions of 23 threats.
Deletions	Recommended deletion of 3 duplicate threats and merging of 2 threats into a single entity.
New Threats	Identified 4 new threats not previously included in the SecRAM catalogue.
Sub-threats	Proposed further specialization of generic threats into more precise sub-threats for 9 of the SecRAM threats. This approach defines several sub-threats under a high-level threat to represent specific types of attacks.
Labels	Categorized identified threats according to attributes like software, hardware, network, complexity, STRIDE, etc.
Public Catalogue Mapping	Each threat was aligned with the closest match in the CAPEC and ATT&CK catalogues.
New Vulnerabilities	15 new vulnerabilities were identified that are not currently present in the catalogue.
Vulnerability Descriptions	The mapping process matched 33 vulnerabilities from the SecRAM catalogue, which were previously listed only by title without descriptions. Precise descriptions were proposed for each of these vulnerabilities.
Public Vulnerability Mapping	All identified vulnerabilities were mapped to the closest match in the CWE catalogue maintained by MITRE.

comprehensive training programs that prepare personnel to effectively handle security challenges.

2) *Categorization based on Threat Vector — Cyber or Non-Cyber*: This categorization divides threats into two main types: digital (cyber) and physical (non-cyber). It enables the aviation sector to better understand and develop strategies to address these diverse types of threats. Analysis of the SecRAM catalogue reveals that non-cyber threats constitute about 63% of entries, suggesting a potential underemphasis on cyber threats. This insight is crucial for security experts and policymakers

responsible for aviation security, as recognizing this imbalance is key to bolstering cyber defences. By maintaining a balanced focus on both traditional physical threats and emerging cyber threats, we can enhance protection for aviation systems in an increasingly digital environment.

3) *Categorization based on Asset Locations — Aircraft or Ground Infrastructure*: This categorization divides threats within the aviation ecosystem into airborne and ground-based categories. This distinction helps determine whether a threat targets the aircraft or ground facilities, such as terminals and

control towers, providing a clearer understanding of where threats are likely to occur and identifying high-risk areas. Such strategic categorization enables tailored security measures, optimizing resource allocation to protect areas of greatest risk. Onboard threats may require advanced cybersecurity for in-flight systems, while ground threats might necessitate enhanced physical security at airports. This approach not only bolsters incident response strategies—with immediate actions for onboard issues and coordinated responses for ground threats—but also supports compliance with diverse regulatory standards for airborne and ground operations.

4) *Categorization based on the SA Life Cycle*: This approach organizes threats based on the various stages of the life cycles of aviation supporting assets. These stages include Produce, Deliver, Deploy and Configure, Operate, Maintain, and Others. This categorization provides a time-based perspective on when and where threats may impact an asset, from its production to its end-of-life. It is critical because it enables stakeholders to identify vulnerabilities early and implement proactive security measures. For manufacturers, this involves strengthening security in the supply chain and production. Operators and maintenance teams can benefit by developing robust operational protocols and maintenance practices during the 'Operate' and 'Maintain' stages to mitigate risks.

5) *Categorization based on Threat Sophistication and Complexity*: This categorization classifies threats based on the level of technology and expertise required for their execution. It divides threats into two categories: 'Simple' threats, such as phishing and eavesdropping, and 'Sophisticated' threats, which require advanced technology like complex cyber intrusions. This categorization is crucial as it enables tailored defence strategies. It assists cybersecurity and physical security personnel in the aviation sector to allocate resources efficiently and develop targeted training programs. Simple threats can be addressed with general awareness campaigns and basic protocols, while sophisticated threats necessitate advanced detection technologies and specialized response teams. This approach also guides policymakers and regulatory bodies to update security standards to effectively combat complex threats.

6) *Categorization based on STRIDE*: The STRIDE model defines six principal types of security threats. These include: Spoofing, where identity impersonation occurs; Tampering, involving the alteration of data, code, memory, and other resources; Repudiation, where an entity can deny accountability for an action; Information Disclosure, the unauthorized exposure of data; Denial of Service, which disrupts or degrades services to end-users; and Elevation of Privileges, where privileges are acquired without proper authorization. Each category signifies a violation of essential security properties critical to maintaining a secure system. This delineation aids security professionals in focusing on specific threats that could potentially compromise the system under examination.

Threat categorization can be highly beneficial for cybersecurity efforts within the aviation sector. It enables organizations to better understand and address potential risks, allocate resources more efficiently, and streamline incident

response strategies. Adopting this approach can significantly enhance defensive postures, response capabilities, and strategic planning, crucial in navigating a dynamic threat landscape.

C. Short- and Long-Term Benefits of Proposed Improvements

The proposed improvements to SecRAM catalogues offer immediate advantages that can be realized near term, enhancing the framework's usability and effectiveness right away.

- *Enhanced Scope and Coverage of SecRAM*: The addition of new threats and vulnerabilities broadens the SecRAM catalogue, ensuring it encompasses a wider array of potential risks. This enhanced scope directly improves the system's resilience against emerging threats, providing a more robust framework for security assessments.
- *Improved Specificity and Mitigation Strategies*: By offering more detailed descriptions and categorizations of threats, the proposed changes enable more targeted and effective mitigation strategies. Security teams can better understand specific threats and apply the most appropriate countermeasures, enhancing overall security efficacy.
- *Increased Completeness and Usability*: The inclusion of detailed vulnerability descriptions and other critical information minimizes the risk of misinterpretation, ensuring users can accurately assess and respond to threats. These improvements make SecRAM a more precise, accurate, and comprehensive tool, leading to better-informed decision-making in the short term.

In addition to the immediate gains, these enhancements are poised to deliver significant long-term benefits, strengthening the overall resilience and trust within the aviation security ecosystem over time.

- *Increased Trust Among Stakeholders*: The comprehensive and up-to-date nature of the revised SecRAM catalogue fosters greater confidence among stakeholders, including ATM system operators, manufacturers, and regulatory bodies. This trust is essential to foster collaboration and ensuring the effective implementation of security measures across the aviation sector.
- *Autonomous Updating and Reduced Maintenance*: Integration with public catalogues like CAPEC, MITRE ATT&CK, and CWE supports continuous and autonomous updates to SecRAM. This self-sustaining mechanism minimizes maintenance efforts and ensures that SecRAM stays current with emerging threats, zero-day vulnerabilities, and exploits, thereby reducing the risk of outdated information.
- *Widespread Adoption and Enhanced Aviation Security*: The improvements position SecRAM as a leading framework for threat and vulnerability assessment within the aviation sector. Widespread adoption of the enhanced SecRAM would contribute to a more secure aviation environment by standardizing threat assessment practices and bolstering overall sector-wide resilience.
- *Improved Risk Management through Labeling and Categorization*: The systematic labeling and categorization of

threats facilitate the development of tailored security policies, awareness programs, and targeted security measures, thereby strengthening the defensive posture of aviation sector organizations.

D. Delimitations and Open Issues

The scope of this work is limited to the analysis the trajectory-based use case presented in the SecAirspace project. This limitation may impact the completeness of the obtained results, potentially excluding other relevant technological, architectural, or procedural environments that could be pertinent to other potential SecRAM applications. Furthermore, the scope of the single use case is restricted to network architecture and does not consider specific details on the implementation of software and services, but only their overall interaction. These limitations were set to provide a concise research environment; however, they restrict the breadth of the analysis and might affect the completeness of the obtained results. Therefore, even though this research provided an insightful gap analysis of the current SecRAM catalogues, we expect future research to apply the proposed methodology to assess how the updated catalogues can serve different use cases. These might include diverse environments, architectures, technologies, and procedures. Future use cases should vary in scope and detail to provide SecRAM with feedback that enhances the security framework's ability to support diverse design and development activities within the ATM context. Additionally, approaches not addressed in this work, such as leveraging taxonomies and ontologies to represent the associations between various threats and vulnerabilities, could also be explored in future research.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This article discusses how the current ATM ecosystem is evolving, driven by the modernization of technologies that enable data-driven services such as TBO. These new services offer opportunities to enhance efficiency, performance, and sustainability within the ATM environment. However, the increased interconnectivity and data-sharing capabilities also introduce cybersecurity challenges that must be addressed from the early design phases. This paper analyzes the SecRAM approach proposed by SESAR in the context of a modern ATM scenario. It highlights the gaps in the current methodology and related catalogues, particularly for modern systems that are highly IT-based and feature enhanced interconnectivity. Improving the SecRAM framework is crucial to ensure the secure and resilient design of future ATM services and architectures. This paper proposes enhancements to SecRAM, including the addition of specific threats and vulnerabilities that were historically less relevant but are increasingly significant in the evolving ATM ecosystem. These enhancements will help cybersecurity professionals better address and mitigate risks in complex infrastructures.

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TABLE A1. THREAT CATEGORIZATION

Categories		Threats listed in SecRAM 2.0																																Total A+B	%
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32		
1A	Software	•		•	•				•		•				•	•	•		•													•	•	13	20
	Hardware		•	•	•									•	•	•			•						•							•	•	13	20
	Physical Infrastructure				•														•			•	•	•			•	•			•	•	26	40	
	Communication Network					•		•		•				•		•				•												•	•	8	12
	Human Factors						•												•	•	•								•				•	20	31
	Media										•	•	•				•								•	•				•		•	12	19	
2A	Cyber	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•			•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	26	41	
	Non Cyber		•	•	•															•	•	•			•	•	•	•			•	•	•	45	70
3A	Aircraft Systems	•	•	•				•		•			•			•					•	•	•				•	•	•		•	•	•	21	33
	Ground Infrastructure	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	60	94
4A	Produce	•	•	•							•						•		•			•										•	•	14	22
	Deliver		•		•														•													•	•	6	9
	Deploy and Configure	•	•	•					•		•					•		•			•													13	20
	Operate	•	•	•		•		•	•	•	•			•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•				•			•	•	44	69	
	Maintenance	•	•	•					•		•					•		•			•													13	20
	Others					•					•	•					•			•						•	•	•		•	•		•	19	30
5A	Simple					•	•			•	•	•				•			•	•				•	•	•	•		•	•		•	27	42	
	Sophisticated	•	•	•	•	•			•	•				•	•	•		•	•			•	•							•	•		•	37	58

Categories		Threats listed in SecRAM 2.0																																		Total A+B	%
		33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	62	63	64				
1B	Software									•																						•	•	13	20		
	Hardware									•		•					•								•									13	20		
	Physical Infrastructure				•	•	•	•			•	•			•			•	•	•		•	•	•	•	•	•	•						26	40		
	Communication Network										•	•			•								•	•	•								•	8	12		
	Human Factors							•	•	•		•	•			•	•				•	•		•					•	•	•	•	•	20	31		
	Media	•	•							•							•																	12	19		
2B	Cyber																																26	41			
	Non Cyber	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	45	70		
3B	Aircraft Systems							•		•	•	•	•			•				•	•						•	•						21	33		
	Ground Infrastructure	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	60	94		
4B	Produce					•	•			•		•									•				•								14	22			
	Deliver																				•			•									6	9			
	Deploy and Configure					•	•			•		•									•													13	20		
	Operate			•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•			•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	44	69		
	Maintenance					•	•			•		•									•													13	20		
	Others	•	•													•		•	•										•	•		•	•	19	30		
5B	Simple	•	•							•	•	•			•	•	•	•				•						•	•		•	•	27	42			
	Sophisticated			•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•		•	•				•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	37	58		

1. Categorization based on types of Supporting Assets, 2. Categorization based on Threat Vector: Cyber vs. Non-Cyber, 3. Categorization based on Asset Locations: Aircraft & Ground Infrastructure, 4. Categorization based on the Supporting Asset Life Cycle, and 5. Categorization based on Threat Sophistication and/or Complexity.